

were screened in the field during the main season.

In F_1 progenies from all crosses, dominance of fertility over complete sterility was observed. F_2 populations from P1/P5 and P1/P6 showed segregation for fertility and complete sterility in a ratio of 15:1. This indicated that thermosensitive male sterility was controlled by two pairs of recessive genes with duplicate inheritance. The remaining three crosses displayed monogenic control of this trait. The test cross progenies from P1/P5 showed 3:1 segregation ($\chi^2=0.0126$). The results suggested two pairs of independent recessive genes

controlling the TGMS trait in UPRI 95-140. Monogenic inheritance observed in the F_2 populations of crosses P1/P2, P1/P3, and P1/P4 was due to the allelic nature of one of the two pairs of recessive genes present in both the parents involved.

Fertility transformation of TGMS plants in segregating populations of crosses depended on the genetic background of the male parents used. In the F_2 generation, average maximum fertility of TGMS plants during spring 1996 was 37.7, 45.3, 60.5, and 65.4% in crosses P1/P5, P1/P6, P1/P2, and P1/P4, respectively, as compared with 41.5% in UPRI 95-140, the female and

TGMS donor parent. Differential behavior of TGMS plants in the F_2 for transformation from fertility to complete sterility was observed during the heading period: 25 Apr to 20 May for cross P1/P5, 1-10 May for P1/P6, 1-25 May for P1/P2, 1-10 May for P1/P4, and 1 May for the TGMS female parent. Eight lines identified with early transformation behavior were 97-7S from P1/P2; 34-2S and 69-2S from P1/P5; 206-8S, 206-9S, and 206-10S from P1/P4; and 79-2S and 79-4S from P1/P6. These lines are being further evaluated for their agronomic performance and for possible exploitation in hybrid breeding. ■

Biochemical markers for characterizing rice genotypes

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Eight frequently used genotypes in the hybrid rice program were characterized on the basis of (1) phenol color reaction; (2) electrophoresis profiles of total soluble seed proteins, albumin, and globulin; and (3) polymorphism with respect to esterase (EST), malate dehydrogenase (MDH), peroxidase (POX), alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH) and glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) isozymes. These genotypes were IR58025A, IR58025B, IR62829A, IRR62929B, IR54742-22-19-3R, IR40750-

82-2-2-3R, IR10198-66-2R, and IR20933-68-21-1-1-2-1R.

Seven genotypes were grouped into two classes on the basis of phenol color reaction; IR20933-68-21-1-1-2-1R was distinct from the others because it did not develop color. A comparison of sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis profiles of soluble proteins, albumin, and globulin revealed maximum polymorphism among the genotypes for the albumin fraction. All the genotypes were distinct from each other except for the A and B lines, in which only the presence of a weak band of approximately 14,000 kD molecular weight differentiated IR58025A from its maintainer line.

Maximum polymorphism was detected in the isozyme patterns of EST and POX, which differentiated all A

and R lines. The greater intensity of a POX band having an Rm of 0.93 differentiated IR58025A from its B line. A faint MDH band having an Rm of 0.67 was detected in IR62829A, but was absent in its corresponding B line. Thus, a combination of the albumin profile with a POX, EST, or MDH isozyme pattern could identify all eight lines studied. The phenol color reaction was useful in verifying the identity of IR20933-685-21-1-1-2-1R. Such characterization is useful in establishing or verifying the identity of a genotype and in differentiating one genotype from another. The uniformity of these patterns within the population of a genotype needs to be tested. The possibility of using isozyme markers to test genetic purity, particularly of A lines, is now being investigated. ■

Identifying molecular markers for the gene(s) governing thermosensitive genic male sterility in rice

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Thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) in rice is advantageous in hybrid seed production compared with three-line breeding. Genetic studies revealed four putative genes imparting thermosensitive male sterility in rice. It was observed that the segregation pattern of this trait in the F_2 , F_3 , and backcrosses indicated that sterility caused by the TGMS trait was controlled by a single recessive gene. It was noted, however, that individual TGMS segregants drawn from the same

F_2 population exhibited a differential pattern for fertility alteration, suggesting the influence of modifier genes. This makes the transfer of this character difficult to achieve, as selection has to be made for the appropriate fertility alteration level in addition to selection for the TGMS trait. Identifying a suitable molecular marker linked to genes of the TGMS trait may therefore aid in selection. The present study aimed at tagging genes pertaining to TGMS through a bulked

segregant analysis. TGMS line SA2, selected from mutagenified populations, was nonallelic to other sources of TGMS genes and was designated as tms4. TGMS and fertile bulks were made from the F₂ population of the cross SA2 (TGMS)/N22 (fertile). Seventy-five operon primers were used to examine polymorphism in SA2, N22,

and bulks. Seventeen polymorphic products were specific to the fertile parent N22 and 19 were specific to the TGMS parent SA2. Of these, the 0.7-kb amplicon of OPA12 and 1.9-kb amplicon of OPS1 were specific to the TGMS trait.

TGMS line ID24 was allelic to Norin PL 12 (tms2) and was nonallelic to SA2.

Earlier studies on tagging the Chinese TGMS source reported that the 1.2-kb amplicon was closely linked. A bulked segregant analysis of the F₂ of the cross ID24/N22 revealed that a 1.2-kb amplicon of OPB19 was specific to TGMS. Further studies related to mapping are in progress. ■

Breeding methods

Heterosis over environments in crosses involving indica and tropical japonica rice cultivars

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The discovery of wide compatibility genes in rice recently shifted the emphasis on enhancing heterosis from intervarietal hybrids to intersubspecific hybrids. We therefore studied the nature and magnitude of heterosis in inter- and intrasubspecific crosses involving improved tropical japonica (J) parents (BSI 10 [P1], BSI 16 [P2], B4116 [P3], and B4122 [P4]) and indica (I) parents (Govind [P5], Manhar [P6], Pant Dhan 4 [P7], Sarjoo 52 [P8], Pant Dhan 12 [P9], and Narendra 359 [P10]). We evaluated all 45 hybrids and parents in a randomized complete block design under environments with

optimum sowing and high fertility (E1), optimum sowing and optimum fertility (E2), and late sowing and high fertility (E3). We studied 10 agronomic traits, including harvest index and grain yield, for heterosis, hetero-beltiosis, and standard heterosis using Pant Dhan 4 as the standard variety.

Analysis of variance indicated a large variation among hybrids and parents. Moderate to high heterosis for yield and agronomic traits across environments was recorded. Trends in the magnitude of heterosis were $I/J > I/I > J/J$ for grain yield and plant height and $I/J > J/J > I/I$ for days to flowering. Standard heterosis for grain yield percentage in the respective E1, E2, and E3 environments ranged from -64.5 to 146.1, -70.4 to 82.2, and -67.2 to 63.8. E1 (optimum sowing and high fertility) gave a better response for heterosis expression.

Higher heterosis in grain yield accompanied heterosis in panicle number, total dry matter and/or

spikelet number, and grain number panicle⁻¹. Almost 95% of the hybrids recorded negative heterosis for flowering and some were earlier by 11-27 d across environments. Hybrids P3/P8 in E1, P4/P6 in E2, and P1/P5 in E3 recorded 19.1, 20.1 and 20.4% standard heterosis for earliness and 146.1, 66.8, and 60.2% for grain yield, respectively. Standard heterosis for height was 2.0-13.7% across environments. Both parents having *Sd1* genes caused F₁ height to increase only slightly. Promising hybrids for direct exploitation were P3/P8, P1/P9, and P1/P10 in E1; P4/P7, P4/P6, and P4/P10 in E2; P4/P7, P7/P9, and P7/P8 in E3; and P3/P8, P4/P7, and P4/P10 over environments. These hybrids showed good prospects for increasing potential yields and per-day productivity in the subtropics. Studies are in progress to improve parents for the thermosensitive genic male sterility trait and resistance against biotic stresses. ■

Plant regeneration from protoplasts of wild rice, *Oryza meyeriana* Bail.

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Oryza meyeriana is a wild rice species distributed in southern China and Southeast Asia. An accession found in China's Yunan Province has a strong resistance to bacterial leaf blight. It is

difficult, however, to transfer the disease resistance character of *O. meyeriana* to cultivated rice (*O. sativa*) by sexual hybridization because of sexual incompatibility between the two species.

Plant regeneration from protoplasts is important for rice breeding and is a prerequisite for genetic manipulation via somatic hybridization. Progress has been made in protoplast culture and regeneration of cultivated rice and other *Oryza* species. Plants have been recovered from cryopreserved calli in

O. meyeriana. Here, we report on successful plant regeneration from protoplasts of this wild rice.

The immature panicles in the stamen and pistil differentiation stage were taken from cryopreserved callus-regenerated plants and used as explants. Calli were induced on N6 medium containing 2 mg L⁻¹ 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, 45 g L⁻¹ sucrose, and 5 g L⁻¹ agar at pH 5.8. Pale yellow primary calli with a dry appearance were transferred to liquid AA2 medium. Fine dispersed calli were